

THE USE OF RIDDLE GAMES TO TEACH SPEAKING TO THE PUPILS AT PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14879047>

Annotation: The article is devoted to speaking lessons in primary schools, using pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching speaking at the beginning level. Riddles are suggested as effective method for developing speaking skills both in classroom and outdoor activities, new interactive methods is highlighted. Also, from interactive methods samples are recommended and illuminated It depicts how to improve students' speaking abilities in second language acquisition in secondary school. It also suggests teachers to improve their learners' pronunciation and fluency by using various tongue twisters and riddles. It proves their benefits for employing in teaching speaking in English based on various famous linguists' theories.

Keywords: primarily school, speaking, interactive, explanatory reading, intonation, method, education, expressive reading, art reading.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the ongoing reforms in the field of education have been noticeably felt in Uzbekistan. The creation of new educational institutions, the opening of modern areas of education and training specialties, as well as correspondence and evening departments, an increase in admission quotas to higher educational institutions are important reforms in this direction. At the same time, great importance is given to reforms related to the study of foreign languages.

Today students are expected to be able to communicate in English since English is one of the international languages and it has become the language of global communication. English also plays important roles in international education because of a lot of textbooks in many technical and scientific fields are available only in English. In Uzbekistan, English is being taught as a foreign language.

There are four skills that the students have to master. Those are listening, speaking, reading and writing. Among the four language skills, speaking is the most important skills in learning besides listening, reading and writing. Speaking is the direct route from one mind to another, and is the way we usually choose when we want to ask a question, or give an explanation. Speaking is a crucial part of second language learning and teaching. Despite its importance for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues.

Speaking is productive skill that can be directly and empirically observed, those observations are invariably colored by the accuracy and effectiveness of test taker's listening skill, which necessarily compromises the reliability and validity of an oral proction test (Brown, 2004:218). If students want to able speak fluently in English, they need to able pronounce phonemes correctly, use appropriate stress and intonation patterns and speak in connected speech.

Speakers of English especially where it is a second language will have to able to speak in range of different genres and situations and they have to be able to use a range of conversational and conversational repair strategies. They will need to be able to survive in typically functional exchanges.

Kids love riddles. They often see them as a very intellectual challenge that can be solved with some thinking outside of the square. Below are 50 riddles that your kids will love to try and solve and you can use them as icebreakers if need be too. Riddles are a great way to add some laughter and humor to your school day, but riddles can serve an ever bigger purpose. When students hear riddles, they will begin to make associations, link what they are learning in the classroom, and come to conclusions about things they already know. For example, a riddle about the moon might connect something your students are learning about in science class.

2. Methods.

There are some methods to enhance pupils speaking skills. Even if your riddles aren't educational, the simple experience of laughter will increase joy in the classroom, and joyful students are more likely to enjoy school and become deeply engaged in their learning. A riddle a day will keep your classroom joyful and ready to learn new things! Enjoy watching your students figure out these riddles and enjoy their laughter when they do.

Here are some riddles for pupils to help get you started!

1. What has a face, but can't smile. Answer: A clock.
2. There is only one word spelled wrong in the dictionary. What is it? Answer: W-R-O-N-G.
3. I can fill up a room, but take no space. What am I? Answer: Light.
4. What is a bunny's favorite kind of music? Answer: Hip hop music.
5. What kind of room has no doors or windows? Answer: A mushroom.
6. What can you catch, but not throw? Answer: A cold.
7. What begins with T, finishes with T, and has T in it? Answer: A teapot.
8. What goes up, but never comes back down? Answer: Your age.
9. What is brown, has a head, and tails, but no legs? Answer: A penny.
10. What room do ghosts avoid? Answer: The living room.

Why Use Riddles on Your pupils?

Riddles can be used to achieve a number of objectives in the ESL classroom. You can use them as warmers and icebreakers, as part of a larger lesson on a specific topic or as your closing activity. Riddles encourage students to think critically and work as a team, where they must practice their English together in order to communicate their ideas, theories and solutions.

The researcher employed an observation to know how the process of teaching learning speaking through riddle game. The observation conducted in one meeting. As the Millan statement there are nine steps in teaching speaking through riddle game, the researcher noted that the entire step was done by the teacher. But, the teaching learning process were not running well. Because, some students were busy with their own activity, some students made noisy and some students guess the word in bahasa.

You can pick and choose riddles to focus on different aspects of English. For example, some riddles may use the vocabulary you wish to review with your students. You can also use riddles to introduce new vocabulary in a fun and engaging way. Riddles, can also be useful for pronunciation, spelling, rhyming or even teaching English idioms. Below are some riddles that are especially relevant for ESL students.

1. Race to Solve the Riddle

Before class, prepare a list of riddles. Depending on the level of your class, decide whether you want to use riddles using simple or advanced English. You can even start with simple riddles, then add more challenging ones later in the activity if you really want to get your students thinking.

Begin the activity by dividing the class into small groups, then give each group a worksheet with the riddles you selected. The groups must race against each other to answer all of the riddles correctly. When a group thinks they've successfully answered all the riddles, have them raise their hand so you can check their work. The first group to answer all riddles correctly wins the exercise.

2. Choose the Best Answer

Again, prepare a list of riddles before class.

Like the previous exercise, you'll begin this activity by dividing the class into small groups. Hand out your riddle sheets to each group, instructing them to start once every group has received a worksheet.

When finished, have each group write their answers to the riddles on the board. Instead of determining the right and wrong answers like you did in the previous activity, let your students vote on what answers they think are the best or most likely to be right. Then, have each group explain why they chose that answer.

Groups with the most votes win the game.

3. Write Your Own Riddles

Creative students will love this activity!

For this exercise, learners must write their own riddles and then try to stump their classmates. Depending on your class proficiency level, you can have students work individually or in small groups to create two or

three riddles. Generally speaking, beginners and intermediate students tend to work best in pairs or small groups. Once they've finished writing their riddles, give each student (or group) a chance to read their riddles to the class. The rest of the class is expected to solve the riddle.

If you really want to give your students the opportunity to explore their creativity while learning English, pair your riddle activities with Fluent U.

Fluent U takes authentic videos—like music videos, movie trailers, news and inspiring talks—and turns them into personalized language lessons.

Brain-teasing Riddles for ESL Students That Are Guaranteed to Be a Hit

Easy riddles

Here are some riddles geared towards beginners. These riddles focus on spelling, pronunciation, specific groups of vocabulary, such as body parts, and how some English words have different meanings.

1. Riddle: How many letters are in the alphabet?

Answer: 11 (t-h-e a-l-p-h-a-b-e-t).

This riddle is ideal for getting students to think about spelling and to review the alphabet.

2. Riddle: What has a face and two hands but no arms or legs?

Answer: A clock.

This riddle focuses in on specific vocabulary related to clocks. It can also encourage a discussion about the many uses or double meanings of English words. For example, face on a person and the face of a clock and hands of a person and the hands of a clock.

3. Riddle: There is a house. One enters it blind and comes out seeing. What is it?

Answer: A school.

This riddle explores a rather common English idiom the relationship between seeing and being enlightened or knowledgeable.

Medium and slightly hard riddles

For your more intermediate students, try some of the following riddles. These riddles will test your ESL students knowledge and understanding of different parts of speech, such as adverbs, and homonyms.

Difficult riddles

These riddles should be saved for your advanced students. The language skills needed to successfully solve them is more complex than the previous riddles mentioned. Students can use these riddles to practice and review grammar rules, as well as exercising their knowledge of vocabulary.

3 Conclusion

From the explanation above it can be concluded that Riddle games is a question, a puzzle, a phrase or statement devised to get unexpected answer. Riddle game can help those who play to arouse their self-confidence, more creatively and decrease the anxiety from acquiring the language.

By using riddle games the students will be able to learn the target language unconsciously and they learnt some new words without any stress on their feeling. Enhancing effective speaking skills through tongue twisters and Comparative study of riddles.

Speaking as a productive skill, seems intuitively the most important of all the four language skills, because it can distinctly show the correctness and language errors that a language learner makes. Pronunciation is one important aspect of speaking English, it can be said that basic skills must be understood before deep learning about speaking. Since our country are not native speakers, most of the students have difficulty understanding and digesting the correct pronunciation in English. The ability to speak using accurate pronunciation is very important. If we do mispronounce while speaking, it makes the listener difficult to understand what we are talking about. Furthermore, it can be one of the factors which can lead to the conversation breakdown. The use of Riddle games can improve students fluency and accuracy in speaking English. Therefore Riddle games is needed to motivate the students to learn about pronunciation.

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